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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Table of contents

INTRODUCTION	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
1. THE ENLIGHT RISE FOCUS GROUPS	5
AIM OF THE FOCUS GROUPS	5
THEMATIC AREAS	5
COMPOSITION.....	6
EXPECTED TASKS.....	7
RECOMMENDED OPERATIVE FRAMEWORK.....	7
OUTPUTS	7
2. ACTION PLAN	8
Links with Erasmus+ CORE GROUPS and THINK TANK	8
3. ROLLOUT OF THE FOCUS GROUPS	8
COMPOSITION AND CREATION	8
OVERVIEW AND MODUS OPERANDI OF THE FOCUS GROUPS.....	9
Focus Group on Climate Change	10
Focus Group on Digital Revolution and Impact of Digitization.....	11
Focus Group on Energy and Circular Economy	11
Focus Group on Equity	12
Focus Group on Health and Well-being	12
TAKEAWAYS, CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD (FUTURE PROSPECTS)	13
ANNEXES	18
Annex 1: Template Participant Profile Focus Group Climate Change.....	18
Annex 2: Visual spreadsheet University Research Interest-Focus - FG “Climate”	20
Annex 3: Visual spreadsheet University Research Interest-Focus - FG “Energy”.....	21

INTRODUCTION

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ENLIGHT is a European University Alliance to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher Education Transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries.

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and more specifically within the Science With and For Society (SWAFS) Work Programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT Alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The main objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) of ENLIGHT RISE is to **create synergies through R&I capacity building**. Complementing the mapping of expertise in the ENLIGHT Think Tank (Erasmus+), WP2 analyses the alliance members' scientific and technological profiles and tries to exploit the synergies leading to maximize ENLIGHT Alliance's competitive advantage (task 2.1). WP2 Research & Innovation Observatory will help identifying ENLIGHT R&I capacities (task 2.2) and WP2 Pilot Focus Groups will lead the strategic orientation for building competitive R&I collaborations among them (task 2.3). At the same time, WP2 Pilot Focus Groups will help Work Package 1 ("Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda") prioritize R&I support activities.

In order to drive competitive joint Research & Innovation initiatives on flagship challenges¹ within the alliance, the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 is working to establish some pilot focus groups on ENLIGHT flagship challenges. These groups will coordinate the emergence and/or expansion of collaborative R&I actions within ENLIGHT and establish an action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications in their specific domain, in close interaction with the R&I Support Group (R&I-SG)² (WP1 Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda).

This active document represents *D12 (D2.4) and describes the rollout of five pilot focus groups (one per flagship area). This document is an update of the D11 (D2.3) and therefore adopts the text of D11 (describing the structural framework, general intent and foreseen tasks of the pilot focus groups), complementing it with the experiences and takeouts of the rollout of the 5 pilot focus groups in project year 2. The text in blue italics are the specific additions for D12 (from the end of page 7 and onwards). The future deliverable D16 (D2.8), to be published in month 36 (August 2024), will further update D11 and D12 describing the outcome and achievements of the pilot focus groups by the end of the project lifespan.*

¹ Flagship areas: Health and Well-Being; Digital revolution; Climate action; Energy transition & Circular Economy; Equity. For more information, please consult this page: <https://enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains> :

² The R&I-SG is a working group of research support officers from all nine universities which aims at identifying synergies that can be achieved in different sources of EC funding; facilitating/incentivizing research collaborations.

1. THE ENLIGHT RISE FOCUS GROUPS

Guidelines for the ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups have been set up in order to give the main information on the aim, thematics, composition, expected tasks and outcomes of the Focus Groups.

AIM OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

The overall objective of these Focus Groups is to **coordinate the emergence and expansion of mission-oriented R&I projects, building on the ENLIGHT alliance R&I capacities and leading to successful grant applications around the flagship challenges.**

This main goal can be decoupled in some specific action lines that will guide the Focus Groups activity:

- ✓ Community building: getting to know each other, the different expertise available in relation to the flagship domain at each institution, and the interest for establishing collaborations;
- ✓ Identification of the right expertise at each university and facilitate the connection between them;
- ✓ Establishment of an action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications; and
- ✓ Activation of pilot R&I projects on flagship domains.

THEMATIC AREAS

The ENLIGHT alliance focuses its action around five big challenges that are key determinants of societal well-being and sustainability (ENLIGHT flagships):

- **Health and Well-being:**
Urban Health with a special focus on (i) the impact of aging populations, especially on brain and mental health, (ii) the impact of environmental exposures and inequalities in healthcare access, and (iii) opportunities for future cities through precision medicine and digital public health.
- **Digital Revolution and Impact of digitization:**
AI for Good in our cities and communities, with a special focus on digital simulation to support decision-making, AI and health, AI and sustainable society.
- **Climate change:**
Climate change and urban development with a special focus on: (i) impact of climate change on land use, socio-ecosystems, relation between cities and surrounding rural areas, (ii) mitigation through improved environmental impact assessment, intersectoral initiatives for climate neutrality.
- **Energy and Circular Economy:**
Energy conversion and transition with a special focus on multidisciplinary approaches to (i) energy transition, (ii) circularity, and (iii) raw material value chain.
- **Equity:**
Addressing polarization in our cities and communities, with a special focus on (i) urban development and marginalization, (ii) access and equity in future cities for long-term sustainability, (iii) sustainable heritage and polarization.

The ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups will correspond to this thematic division meaning there will be five Focus Groups, one for each of the ENLIGHT Flagships.

COMPOSITION

1. Procedure for the composition of the Focus Groups

The Focus Groups' members are nominated by the universities according to their profile and qualifications, which should be relevant to the competences of the flagship domain and aligned with the following profile description.

The composition may evolve depending on the need for more specific expertise, skills and/or interest for collaboration.

2. The focus group member profile

The Focus Groups are ideally composed by a variety of profiles that will enrich the co-creation process, including (among others) the following ones:

Scientific profiles: Researchers at different stages of career having expertise in the thematic areas of the five ENLIGHT flagship areas, more specifically:

- ✓ Senior researchers specialized in a theme linked to the focus group specific flagship domain (from R3 (Established Researcher) to R4 (Leading Researcher), as defined by Euraxess research profile descriptors³); and
- ✓ Junior researchers with any background that could contribute to any of the flagship areas (R2 (Recognised Researcher, i.e. PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)).

Research and Support staff profiles:

- ✓ One to two ENLIGHT universities' research support officers (RSOs) per focus group. These RSOs may be also part of the ENLIGHT R&I Support Group.

3. Additional recommendations to be considered for the composition of the focus groups

- ✓ Gender balance should be encouraged;
- ✓ One to two researcher representatives per university per group (ideally one junior and one senior researcher according to the definition set above in section 2);
- ✓ In the light of the synergies and complementarities between the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ and ENLIGHT RISE initiatives, the participation of researchers already members of ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Core Groups is welcome;
- ✓ Each Focus Group should be research and innovation-based.

³ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/europe/career-development/training-researchers/research-profiles-descriptors>

EXPECTED TASKS

Members of the focus groups are expected to carry out the following (non-exhaustive) list of tasks:

- ✓ **Participation in, and when decided so, coordination of a Focus Group;**
- ✓ **Identify and encourage research and innovation collaborations within the ENLIGHT alliance context:**
 - Share and exchange expertise in R&I in the flagship domains;
 - Initiate R&I initiatives in the flagship field at the local university level;
 - Identify new research collaborations.
- ✓ **Undertake R&I project collaborations:**
 - Share and exchange R&I opportunities;
 - Identify relevant calls for proposals;
 - Develop innovative collaborative research projects, involving a minimum of 3 ENLIGHT universities;
 - Develop bottom-up collaborations.
- ✓ **Define and update a road map for each -group;**
- ✓ **Foster synergies and complementarities with ENLIGHT education and training activities;**
- ✓ **Liaise with ENLIGHT Erasmus+ think tank (see section below "Action plan/ links with Erasmus+ Core Groups) in terms of new research opportunities, collaborations and priorities for local partners.**

RECOMMENDED OPERATIVE FRAMEWORK

- ✓ During the first months, it is expected that the members of each group will meet once a month to get to know each other, identify relevant initiatives for collaboration and be able to propose a road map for the group.
- ✓ Each focus group will be led by a leading trio with rotating coordination. The leading trio will be nominated during the first meetings of the group.
- ✓ The focus group will count with managerial and administrative support by the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 team.

OUTPUTS

During the first round of the Focus Groups there are three main expected outputs:

- **Draft road map.** The focus group members will jointly initiate and develop a road map for their group;
- **Short list of complementary research themes.** The focus groups will identify common research topics/ priorities and sub-topics/ priorities to drive joint collaborations/ proposals;
- **External funding opportunities.** The focus groups will identify and should respond to at least one research and innovation call for proposals.

2. ACTION PLAN

As detailed above, each focus group will propose its road map to prioritize and develop its own actions. Each group will have to describe its action plan, the ambition and the planned activities. A template will be proposed to them containing the following items:

- **Action description:**
 - o summary, expected impact and results, complementarity/expertise of partners;
 - o Innovative and strategic aspects of the action;
 - o Long-term goals and sustainability of the cooperation;
 - o European/International call identified (if any) & deadline foreseen.
- **Reverse Schedule;**
- **Expected and Desired Impact on ENLIGHT Flagships/Europe/Society.**

Links with Erasmus+ CORE GROUPS and THINK TANK

In order to reinforce synergies and complementarities between the education and the research and innovation components of the ENLIGHT alliance, a foreseen development and sustainability element for the focus groups is to use the existing ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Think Tank structure. The ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Think Tank is a space for innovation and interconnecting know-how in the flagship domains. It is an inter-university sharing platform regrouping the Erasmus+ core groups (education component of the Alliance) across the nine universities. It enables the members to share the data and milestones of their flagship domain and to identify transversal topics within the flagship areas.

The Think Tank would be then seen as an umbrella for both the education and research and innovation components of the ENLIGHT alliance, enabling the exchange of information, synergies and complementarities with the two independent subgroups (the Core Groups and the Focus Groups) per thematic area.

3. ROLLOUT OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

COMPOSITION AND CREATION

With the publication of D11 in M24, the guidelines for the pilot focus groups (FGs) had been set and thus the attention switched towards the composition and start of the FGs.

Deviating from the General Agreement (GA), WP2 esteemed it best to immediately create five FGs (one per flagship domain) instead of starting only with one on 'health & well-being' and subsequently an additional two on 'climate change' and 'energy & circular economy', as foreseen in the GA. With the finality to foster new R&I collaborations and work towards joint project proposals at the end of project year 3, WP2 considered it best to create all 5 FGs as soon as possible for its members to have the maximum amount of time possible to grow towards joint collaborations.

At the start of project year 2 all partner institutions were asked to seek or nominate their institutional representatives for each FG. More specifically, each partner university (PU) was asked to delegate to each FG 1 senior and 1 junior researcher in the specific field of interest of the FG, along with 1 research support (RS) administrator. To secure the connection with the R&I Support Group (R&I-SG) created in WP1, it was advised to appoint as the RS administrator an active member of WP1 and/or the R&I-SG.

PIs approached this question in different ways; while some PUs nominated for each FG the same members as for the Core Groups of the ENLIGHT E+ programme to keep a general overview and connection, others launched an internal call for candidates, whilst still others approached and nominated specific researchers directly. Most, if not all, administrative staff delegated to the FGs are either the PU's ENLIGHT RISE institutional contact point/programme manager, or indeed the PU's (thematic) member of WP1 and/or the R&I-SG.

Due to the different nomination processes, finalizing the composition of the FGs took several months and was but completed by December 2022 (M28) upon which doodles were sent out to gather a first (online) meeting. This led to all 5 FGs celebrating their kick-off meeting in January 2023 (M29). Since, and prior to the 2023 summer recess, all 5 FGs have held multiple meetings.

As a result, 5 thematic pilot focus groups have already been created (i.e. 2 more and 2 years earlier than projected in the GA). During the first months, all 5 FGs have focussed their attention on getting to know each other and each other's research interests, defining the specific focus of the thematic FG, and starting up thematic subgroups.

What follows, is an account of each FG's activities and workplan, followed by a general conclusion and listing of interim takeaways.

OVERVIEW AND MODUS OPERANDI OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

All FGs celebrated their individual kick-off meeting in January 2023 in a similar way.

After a general presentation by the WP2 lead on the intent and expectations of the pilot focus groups, all FGs debated on how to progress and to decide on which research fields to focus. With each flagship domain being very broad and only vaguely defined (i.e., containing a huge variety of different research fields/topics) all 5 FGs initially felt the need to clearly define their focus/working theme of interest.

Considering that almost all FG members did not meet each other earlier, the need was felt to create a clear view on the expertise (project track record, research focus, and expectations) of all FG members. Thereto, a flagship area specific participant profile template was created for all FG participants to fill out (cf. Annex 1 – template participant profile as created for the FG on climate change). Since the FG members are considered representatives of their home institutions' research community for the entire research field linked to the flagship area, the participant profile also inquired into the PU's focus areas and specific expertise on the flagship domain overall.

The goal was that information obtained through these profiles would surface possible linkages and automatically indicate which research topics the FG should/could focus on to start up new research collaborations amongst the ENLIGHT PUs.

This however did not concretize in all FGs; for some it worked and served as a roadmap towards selecting a focal topic, other FGs sought a different way to determine their central topic(s) and way forward.

Below an account is given on the activities and main decisions taken per FG with respect to the roadmap/action plan and the way ahead:

Focus Group on Climate Change

The FG kicked off January 26th, 2023, and met on June 1st, 2023, for the forth time.

The filled-out participant profiles proved insufficient to draw workable conclusions, partly because the questionnaire was filled out too personal by the researchers (i.e., focussing on their own research (interests)) and not from an institutional point of view, leading to too diverse and specific research fields which did not allow to detect broad/general commonalities.

The FG therefore decided to relaunch the exercise by asking each PU to identify a maximum of 5 research topics of interest (\approx priorities) for their research community on which they would like to engage into joint research collaboration with the other ENLIGHT PUs. The received topics were then put into a spreadsheet for each PU to indicate which of the stated research field they have interested researchers for within their own institution. The idea was that this would make it possible to identify – within the broad field of the flagship area – specific research topics to investigate probable collaboration efforts between PUs.

With the help of the (WP1) R&I-SG, this spreadsheet was expanded with a list of upcoming and foreseen Horizon Europe calls. PUs were asked to discuss this list internally and indicate whether their research community bears researchers interested in engaging into possible project proposal writing efforts for one or more of these calls.

The spreadsheet did not miss its effect and outlaid possible topics for collaboration. Based on its outcomes, 2 subgroups have been created: one on “aerosol-cloud interactions” and another on “development of climate services”. These subgroups are being led by one FG researcher per subgroup who will set up (online) meetings inviting all PUs to send their interested researchers to these meetings to discuss and examine possibilities for joint research collaborations on the specific topic, and investigate the probability to engage into a joint research proposal within the near future.

A next FG meeting will be held in October to examine the progress and viability of the subgroups and assess whether additional subgroups could be created based on the information in the spreadsheet and/or whether a different approach for different focus research topics should be adopted/sought.

The spreadsheet will remain as a database of the thematic interests for collaborations per PU in the flagship domain.

Focus Group on Digital Revolution and Impact of Digitization

With a kick-off meeting on January 9th, 2023, the FG “Digital” met for the third time on June 5th, 2023.

During the second FG meeting, and based on the participant profiles, three focus areas were selected: ‘Robotics’, ‘Cybersecurity’, and ‘Extended reality’. Three researchers volunteered to set up a topic specific meeting with colleagues from other PUs to investigate potential joint collaborations on these topics.

Alongside, the FG members were attracted by the programme of the European Dialogue & AIMDay on the topic of digital health, jointly organized by the ENLIGHT RISE WP5 and ENLIGHT E+ WP5 and scheduled for May 25th, 2023, in Galway. The FG decided 1) that some members would attend this event to investigate potential opportunities, and 2) that a next meeting would be postponed until after the event.

The third FG meeting highlighted that the AIMDay disclosed some potential for collaborations on digital health and extended reality in psychology. Individual researchers will follow this up and perhaps take contact with the FG Health & Well-being since there appear to be many influences and points of contact between the FG “Digital” and the FG “Health”. To that purpose a Discord environment has been set up to rapidly exchange information amongst the members of the FG “Digital”.

Concerning the three subgroups, insufficient potential was found regarding ‘extended reality’. The other two subgroups still have to meet for the first time.

Considering the above, and the diminishing interest and attendance at this FG, the members decided to engage into bilateral contacts and to postpone a next meeting of the FG “Digital” until November-December 2023 to then assess what came out of the bilateral contacts and to reassess possibilities for joint research collaborations.

Focus Group on Energy and Circular Economy

Starting with its kick-off on January 24th, 2023, the FG has met a fourth time on May 15th, 2023.

FG “Energy” has followed a similar path as FG “Climate” in the sense that it also created a spreadsheet to outlay potential links for cooperation based on PU’s main topics of interest and their specific interest regarding existing and foreseen Horizon Europe calls.

This exercise identified 4 clusters of linked research themes with sufficient interest of PUs, leading to the creation of 2 subgroups: one on “Energy storage and production with prime focus on hydrogen”, and another on “Environmental innovations and circular economy, LCA”. Separate meetings will be organized by these subgroups before the end of September 2023 to study concrete possibilities for collaboration.

Regarding the remaining two topics “Positive energy districts” and “Nature based solutions for buildings” already 2 ENLIGHT consortia (respectively ‘E-PED’ and ‘NB²E’) had been created through the [Ghent University Call for ENLIGHT Scientific Research Networks](#). These consortia will proceed with their preparations for 2 project proposals each and will – through the FG “Climate” – invite the remaining PUs to join the proposal once its framework is more concrete.

The FG will meet again in October 2023 to discuss the progress on each of the themes/subgroups.

Focus Group on Equity

After its first meeting on January 12th, 2023, FG Equity has met a second time on the 23rd of March 2023.

The FG first sought on how to define the scope of/on equity but agreed on its delimitation through the general description of the flagship domain's key themes on the ENLIGHT website (<https://www.enlight.eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains>).

The participant profiles and the received list of institutional focus topics did indeed demonstrate potential and viable interest to start up joint research collaboration, and the idea was launched/accepted to work towards 1 specific Horizon Europe call: HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-04: The interrelation between social, cultural, and political identities, as well as the sense of belonging, and democracies.

The FG discussed whether to start the FG activities with one overall transdisciplinary topic, two sub-themes, or whether to work with small groups working out ideas and afterwards bringing concrete concepts for proposals into the general focus group meeting. The FG finally decided to create two subgroups focussing on: 1. environmental transition policies and social justice, and 2. identity, belonging and interrelation between social culture and political identities in democracy.

Since this second meeting (March 23rd, 2023) the FG has not met again, however both subgroups are working separately investigating possible project proposals. A follow-up general meeting will be held in September 2023.

Focus Group on Health and Well-being

The FG kicked-off on January 23rd, 2023, with a fourth meeting on June 1st, 2023.

Alike the FGs "Climate Change" and "Energy", the participant profiles did not offer a clear result on how to proceed within this FG and thus also FG "Health" launched a spreadsheet for each PU to identify their main topics of interest for joint collaborations as well as the Horizon Europe calls their research community would be interested in. This exercise is still on-going and extended towards the search for possibilities through regional/local/national funding schemes.

Nevertheless, during this process two subgroups have been created: one on "aging" and one on "nursing". They will organize separate meetings inviting all PUs' researchers interested in the respective topic to attend and discuss possibilities and opportunities for joint research and/or project proposals on the respective topics.

Alongside, FG "Health" has served as forum for PUs to share information on individual projects and to launch calls for partners regarding already existing project proposal writing initiatives. Also, based on

the experiences during the AIMDays on Digital Health (organized by WP5), a possible link with FG “Digital” is being explored.

After summer recess 2023, the next FG meeting will follow-up on both the spreadsheet and the progress of the subgroups.

TAKEAWAYS, CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD (FUTURE PROSPECTS)

After one semester of activities, all five FGs are well underway. They all have been able to define research topics to focus on. Though the road to successful and sustainable joint research collaboration is still long and uncertain and finding the suitable modus operandi for every FG proved a real quest, we consider the start-up phase successful and promising.

The activities foreseen during the first semester of project year 3 by each FG will be crucial to obtain real and effective results (e.g. submitted or ready to submit project proposals) by the end of the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan.

Five months of trial and error during the meetings of the FGs has given us certain insights and enables us to draw preliminary conclusions on what works, what doesn't, how realistic our initial action plan for the pilot focus groups (D11) was, good practices, and no-goes. Below a list of some of the preliminary findings and deviations in the rollout of the FG according to the action plan projected in D11.

- *Proposing a road map/action plan per FG did not prove realistic; FGs grow organically.*
As written in the GA, Chapter 2 of D11 envisioned each FG to propose a detailed road map on their modus operandi and activities. This appeared to be too administrative, too complex, and moreover a letdown for the researchers. The road map was therefore discarded after the kick-off meeting of all FGs. Especially since most time spent in the start-up phase went into getting to know the other members of the FG. FGs function best when taking swift decisions and working by trial and error. Evidence hereof is that 3 FGs organically evolved towards the same successful modus operandi.
- *Meeting once a month proved too challenging and unrealistic for most researchers.*
*The FG are on-top-off activities for both researchers and administrative staff. The initial plan to meet once a month turned out to be unrealistic given the complex/full agenda of most researchers. Given that the FG members are considered representatives of their PU community on the broad flagship domain, furthermore, required many of the FG members to consult internally to be able to outlay and define their PUs priorities and views. This takes time and effort and could not all be balled up in one month. Defining a date to meet already proved challenging by itself considering the packed agendas.
Meeting every 8-10 weeks in the beginning, and then later every 3 months seems more realistic.*
- *The envisioned rotating coordination by a leading trio proved not to be feasible.*
As already mentioned, the participation of researchers and administrative staff in FGs, is mostly on-top-off and most members have a busy and stretched schedule. Although the intention for the FGs is that they are ‘for and by’ the researchers, it has proven almost impossible to find a researcher willing to take up the (organizational) lead of the FG. Only one researcher accepted and thus in

practice all but one (FG “Equity”) of the pilot focus groups have all been organized and are led by the WP2 lead. Probably the facts that chairing a meeting also costs time to prepare the meetings and that most members do not really know each other also played a role here.

- *Granting protected time for community building activities related to the FG is unrealistic for most.*
The ENLIGHT RISE project proposal foresaw for FG members to receive protected time to work for the FGs, and thus be acquitted of some of their tasks within their institution or to receive a (financial) incentive/benefit. Due to internal institutional regulations, this however is not possible nor common practice in most, if not all, PUs and therefore the involvement in the FGs remains on-top-off and voluntary.
- *Top-down forcing of researchers does not work well and is not productive.*
The FG have been sprouted top-down whilst most (successful) research collaborations originate bottom up. This was visible during the composition phase of the FGs. It was often hard to find researchers willing to invest time in a trajectory towards a pilot project with peers they did not know and a high risk of failure. Especially since it is all on-top-off (cf. above point). Drop-out has been significant and – although possibly also related to full schedules – it has been challenging to keep researchers interested in the start-up phase when no clear result could be guaranteed.
- *Researchers are unfamiliar with represent their institutional research community.*
FG members are expected to represent their institutional community on the concerned flagship domain. As also experienced in the E+ Core Groups, this is often difficult for researchers/academics due to the vastness of the flagship domain (see next point) and due to the pressure of their own personal interests, needs and expectations. This results in FG participants with different starting points: while some are interested in the complete picture of the flagship domain within the PUs, others are only focussed on their own topics of interest and cannot/do not outlay the complete flagship domain picture of their institution. PUs who have RS administrators dedicated at capturing the complete blueprint of a certain domain within their institutional community tackle this by assisting their FG participant. However not all PUs have such dedicated RS administrators at their disposal.
- *The flagship domains are too broad and vaguely defined.*
The ENLIGHT flagship domains each represent various and different research fields making it hard for focussed researchers to have an overall overview on what is going on within their institution on all related research topics that fall under the respective flagship domain. Having researchers around the table who topic wise are not directly linked, makes it challenging for the FG to quickly identify possibilities for joint research collaboration. E.g. in the FG “Health” you might have a neurologist, paediatrician, dietitian and a dentist around the table. Not only is it hard for them to have an overview on the research conducted in the different fields, their own research is often far away from the topics studied by the other FG members. As mentioned in the point above, institutional RS administrators with a complete overview of their institutional activities can tackle this, but this is not a luxury available to all PUs.

- Junior (early career) researchers are harder to involve.
Contrary to the expectations, junior researchers are less involved in the FGs. Although they are at the start of their career and we thus expected them to seize the opportunity to expand their network via the FGs, it has been harder to keep them on board. We suspect this is linked to their full agendas and limited time since they focus mainly on their own activities to pump up their curriculum.
- It is not imperative for all PUs to participate to all FGs
Linked to the reasons mentioned in both previous points, and since every PU has their own research focusses, not all PUs participate to all FGs. This is widely accepted within the FGs and in a natural way limits the amount of people around the table making it sometimes easier to take quick decisions on the way forward or to decide on the research topics to be selected. It does however remain a point of attention since e.g. the FG "Digital" experienced a lack of critical mass to make any progress in its last meeting.
- The foreseen link with the Think Tank / E+ Core Groups is not a first priority, yet...
Time is money, especially in the stretched agendas of researchers and educators. As mentioned above, obtaining the overview on a flagship domain already requires time and effort and the FG timeline is limited. Hence, engaging with the E+ Think Tank/Core Groups is not a priority at this point and all attention is geared towards the start-up of new research collaborations. Notwithstanding, we do still believe in the necessity and benefit of linking the Focus and the Core groups, and foresee this to happen in a later stage, as is envisioned in the follow-up E+ project proposal for ENLIGHT 2.0.
- The timeline of the Horizon Europe calls does not favour the FG timeline.
Listing the existing and foreseen Horizon Europe call deadlines made clear that for some topics, either the most relevant call had already been closed at the FG kick-off meeting or the deadline was too nearby to write an effective and successful project proposal considering this is a lengthy process. Notwithstanding, WP2 decided to launch at once all 5 FGs in order to tackle this issue considering much time goes into getting acquainted with the peers, reality shows that many of the upcoming deadlines in Horizon Europe (HE) are unrealistic because of the extra lengthy process needed by a consortium of partners who hardly knew each other beforehand to agree on a set of joint research activities to include in a successful project proposal to be submitted during the timeline of the RISE project. Future HE work programmes will – of course – always be scrutinized. However, some FGs and researchers have therefore shifted their attention towards regional/national calls in order to try to submit joint proposals before M36 of the RISE project. They realise however it will be harder/impossible for other ENLIGHT PUs to become (financial) beneficiaries in those calls. This reality has made it harder to keep senior researchers interested in, and on board of, the FGs.
- Finding additional funding for the FG mobility looms as a future priority.
We suspect that funding for mobility will become in demand once proposal writing becomes more concrete and FG members will want to meet to advance their project.

- Creating linkages takes time.
(Senior) researchers mostly have their portfolio of colleagues they collaborate with. Expecting them to swiftly go into project proposals (writing) with new (unknown) partners and researchers (sometimes perhaps involving having to omit their usual collaborators) takes confidence and thus time. This does not favour the abovementioned strict timeline of the ENLIGHT RISE project. To increase mutual trust and confidence, it may be useful for the researchers (FG members) to meet in person. We will therefore explore how to facilitate this through the Travel Awards (cf. GA task 2.3.2, page 84)
- Researchers are interested in expanding their network through the ENLIGHT consortium.
Participating researchers do show interest in a system of close partner universities with a preferred status. The level of interconnectivity and the offered research support amongst the PUs appeals. However, as mentioned above, most (senior) researchers already have a portfolio of collaborating (inter)national researchers, and creating new (research) relationships takes time.
- Links appear and function with other ENLIGHT WPs
The help of the ENLIGHT RISE WP1 R&I Support Group was vital to list the available funding calls and the experience at the ENLIGHT RISE WP5 AIMDay in Galway led to new possibilities and cross-overs between FGs. This is a clear example that the FG fit well within the general intent of the ENLIGHT RISE programme.
- The tools created by ENLIGHT (RISE) are of use to the FGs
The already existing tools created by the ENLIGHT project, and those in the pipeline, answer to many questions raised during the FG meeting, and have already proven their purpose for the FGs. We did notice however that they are still underknown by most researchers. Herein lies an opportunity and task for the FGs. We will thus vastly promote the ENLIGHT tools amongst the FG members to boost their usage and fame. Amongst others it concerns the following tools:
 - Partner search: <https://enlight-eu.org/contact/partner-search>
 - Peers search: <https://enlight-eu.org/contact/find-your-enlight-peers>
 - Expertise search: <https://enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/r-i-observatory>
 - Digital Matching tool: to be finalized during project year 3
 - ENLIGHT repository of good practices on research impact: <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/>
 - ENLIGHT toolkit for self-assessment of universities research impact awareness, literacy and readiness: <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment>
 - R&I Observatory: <https://observatory.enlight-eu.org/>
 - The toolkit for (young) researchers: <https://www.enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/r-i-support-and-collaborations/726-toolkit-for-researchers>
 - Open Science ambassadors: <https://www.enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/open-science/ambassadors>
 - ENLIGHT Impact Ambassadors: <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/ambassadors>
 - Mapping dashboards: on the internal SharePoint
 - ENLIGHT (RISE) funding opportunities: <https://www.enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/awards-additional-funding> & <https://www.enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/funding>

➤ *The spreadsheet has proven its use and can be considered a good practice.*

The Excel-file created for 3 FGs to quickly outlay possible linkages and possibilities for joint proposal writing was effective and helpful. Based on its outcomes, FGs were enabled to instantly view which research field they should focus their attention at (and create subgroups). As an additional advantage, they remain as a database/repository of the thematic interests for collaborations per PU in the respective flagship domains.

See annexes 2 and 3 for a visual outlay of the spreadsheet for FG “Climate” and FG “Energy”.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Template Participant Profile Focus Group Climate Change

University

Select your Institution.

Department

Mention your department.

Your name
Function

Email: Email address

Bibliography link: Link to publication list, of ORCID/ResearcherID

Key words:

Describe your research expertise in a couple of key words.

Research Focus:

- Short listing of your research interest.

Experience in European or other international projects:

Short list the main relevant EU projects you participated in and your role in the project. If possible add a link to the project website.

When applicable highlight what you can bring into a consortium

Available data, samples or cohorts or relevant papers in the field

List what might be relevant

Available infrastructure - equipment

List what might be relevant

Relevant network contacts

Mention where relevant your network of stakeholders, interest groups, expert panels, societies. Feel free to also add interested colleagues from your university.

What would you like to gain from the ENLIGHT “Climate change” focus group?

What should these online meetings need to offer, so you would partake in them on a regular basis? What should be the short-term or long-term result of these focus groups?

What thematic areas are of interest to you?

List your thematic areas, e.g. urban development – land use – carbon use – socio-eco-systems - biodiversity – environmental behaviour – energy production - etc.

Health Horizon Europe call topics of interest to you

- If you have already identified relevant European calls that are of interest to you, you can mention them here.

